

The Influence of Dance Learning on the Development of Self-Confidence in Children Aged 5-6 Years at RA Khairu Ummah, Purwodadi Village, Sunggal District, Deli Serdang Regency, Academic Year 2022/2023

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to explain that there was a significant effect of learning dance on the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years at RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal for the 2022/2023 Academic Year. The type of research used in this research is quantitative research using experimental methods. The results of the hypothesis test, "Independent Sample Test" in the Equal variances section are assumed to know the Sig value. (2-tailed) is $0.000 < 0.05$ meaning that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Also, the consulted t_{count} obtained is greater than t_{table} , namely $2.00 < 6,761 > 2.65$. Thus it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the average results of increasing the confidence of children aged 5-6 years at RA Kairu Ummah in the creative dance learning group (experiments) and traditional dance learning groups (control).

INTRODUCTION

Education is very important in improving the quality of human resources because education is a human effort towards student maturity. Education must start from an early age because nowadays the process of children's growth and development is quite rapid. Many Early Childhood Education (PAUD) opportunities are focused on stimulation from the environment because children go through stages of growth and development.

According to Wiyani (2014), one of the standard levels of achievement of social-emotional development for children aged 5-6 years is being able to show self-confidence. Self-confidence is an aspect of social development that must be developed and stimulated from an early age. In line with Byrnes' explanation (Hasnida, 2015) explains that in early childhood education children will learn to become independent individuals, able to socialize, confident, have great curiosity, can express ideas, want to learn, and are enthusiastic about learning.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that self-confidence is important to develop because self-confidence is needed to support children's lives, especially in interacting with their environment. Hasnida (2015) states that self-confidence is an attitude that will help someone to interact in social life. Self-confidence is a person's attitude in believing and showing their potential to support social interactions with the surrounding environment. According to Wiyani (2014), the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years is characterized by being able to tell stories in front of the class, being able to ask and answer questions, being able to express opinions, and working independently.

Based on the results of initial observations, it was concluded that of the 20 orchid group children, there were 5 children, or around 25% who were able to show a confident attitude, while 15 children, or around 75% still lacked self-confidence, the evidence was that they lacked self-confidence, did not lead prayers, were embarrassed to sing in front of friends and teachers in class, not imitating dance movements, even though the teacher teaches that children still ask the teacher for help. The cause of this problem is that the learning methods implemented by teachers are also less varied. Teachers often apply the lecture method during learning. The lecture method applied by teachers can stimulate children's language development but does not provide opportunities for children to play an active role in learning. The learning methods and activities applied by teachers have been able to develop children's abilities in language, cognitive, and artistic aspects, but have not been able to develop children's self-confidence optimally. Therefore, teachers need to apply learning methods that can optimally develop children's self-confidence.

Based on the problems above, one solution that can be taken to overcome the problem of lack of self-confidence in young children is to implement "dance learning". This is confirmed by the opinion of Mulyani (2016, p. 49) who explains that dance is Indonesia's cultural heritage which

must be developed and preserved by the ever-changing development of society. Dancing is an easy tool to organize and train children's movements. Children are free to express their movements according to their wishes, but safely and positively. Dance is an art that is directly related to human body movements. Early childhood dance is a process where children can control and interpret body movements, manipulate objects, and increase body-mind harmony. In connection with this, the researcher wants to conduct research with the title "The Effect of Learning Dance on the Self- Confidence of Children Aged 5-6 Years at RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal Academic Year 2022/2023".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Children's Confidence

According to Wulandari, et al (2019), self-confidence is the potential to solve problems well and entertain other people. In developing children's self- confidence, the role of parents is to be good listeners, model mutual respect, provide opportunities to show themselves, help, train children's independence, direct children to be more optimistic, develop interests and encouraging skills, solving problems together, helping, building communication with adults, and guiding them so they can prepare for the future.

According to Lauster (Ardiyana, et al, 2019), self-confidence consists of several aspects: 1) optimism is the positive attitude of someone who is always aware of everything about themselves, their desires, and abilities, 2) self- confidence in their abilities is the positive attitude of someone who truly understands your actions, 3) tolerance is an attitude of respect, 4) ambition is a state of being aware of the consequences, 5) security is a feeling of not being afraid and worried about facing the future, 6) independence is a person's positive behavior and is not dependent on other people, 7) adapting is positive behavior and interacting with the environment to feel suitable and worthy of being in a new environment.

The characteristics of children's self-confidence are: able to interact with other people, being confident in themselves, being active, creative, and energetic, able to work together and have a leadership spirit, being happy to experiment and try new things, being independent, able to tell stories in front of the class, able to ask questions, be able to answer questions, be able to express opinions.

Dance Learning

Early childhood dance is a process or effort to educate children to control and interpret body movements, manipulate the movement of objects, and increase harmony between body and mind (Lestari, et al, 2019).

Movements in learning dance in early childhood certainly have their characteristics. One of the movements carried out must include the child's world, which is full of joy and pleasure.

Mulyani (2016) explains that the characteristics of dance learning in early childhood include:

1. The subject or name of the dance to be taught must be close to the child's life. Generally, children like things that are close and attract their attention. Children unconsciously imitate movements such as birds flying, chickens eating, goats walking, etc. Therefore, determining dance learning topics should be based on movements that children often encounter and like.

2. Simple form of movement. Forms that are suitable for children are movements that are not difficult, but the characteristics of children are that they cannot stand still for too long, and are active, agile, and fast, which depicts joy and pleasure. In this case, teachers must pay attention to both (simple movements and skilled and active movements) when teaching movement and dance.

3. Accompanied by cheerful music. Music is what children like most. There is no day without music while studying in the classroom or outside the classroom. Accompanied by music, children enthusiastically learn to dance. Child-friendly accompanying music for the dance is of course music that depicts joy and cheerfulness, such as the song "Look at My Garden".

The research that supports this research is Milvi Silastri's research (2022), "The Influence of Creative Dance Movements on the Self-Confidence of Children Aged 5-6 Years in PAUD Bandar Agung Village, South Bengkulu". Based on the results of research conducted by researchers regarding the influence of creative dance movements on the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years in PAUD Bandar Agung Village, South Bengkulu. The results of the paired samples test on control class pre-test data with control class post-test data obtained a value of $p = 0.104 > 0.05$, which means there is no influence of gymnastics movements on the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years in PAUD Bandar Agung village, South Bengkulu.

Ha: There is a significant influence between learning dance on the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years at RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal in the 2022/2023 academic year.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used in this research is quantitative research using experimental methods.

The research was carried out at RA Khairu Ummah located on the street of Mesjid Dusun IV, Purwodadi Village, Sunggal District, Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra Province.

The population in this study were all class B children aged 5-6 years at RA Khairu Ummah with a total of 60 people consisting of 20 class B-1, 20 class B-2, and 20 class B-3.

This research consists of three stages, starting from the preparation stage, the implementation stage, and the final stage. The design in this study used a post-test-only control group design. The two groups received different treatments and then measurements were taken. The experimental class was group B-1 which was given treatment in the form of learning creative dance arts and group B-3 was given treatment in the form of learning traditional dance arts. The data collection instrument used by researchers was to use observation techniques. The data analysis technique in this research is descriptive statistical techniques. What is carried out consists of validity and reliability tests, and then normality and homogeneity tests are carried out using IBM SPSS.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Instrument Validity and Reliability Test

The results of calculating the validity of the instrument using IBM SPSS Statistics 20, then the results are conditioned on the r_{table} with a significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$). The statement is said to be valid if $r_{count} > r_{table}$, conversely if $r_{count} < r_{table}$ then the instrument is declared invalid. The r_{table} value with $N=20$ and a significance level of 5% are 0.444. Based on the results of the validity of the statement items in the self-confidence observation sheet for children 5-6 years old, all statement items were declared valid, because in each statement item the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$.

Reliability analysis of instrument statements was carried out on valid instrument statements, invalid ones were not used to collect data. Based on the results of IBM SPSS Statistics 20 calculations, the results of calculating the reliability of the self-confidence questionnaire for children 5-6 years old were obtained r_{11} and after consulting the interval scale for the level of correlation strength, the correlation coefficient for the self-confidence observation sheet statement for children 5-6 years old was classified as high, $r_{count} > r_{table}$ or Cronbach's Alpha $0.749 > 0.444$ then the instrument is declared to have high reliability.

Testing Requirements Analysis Normality test

The normality test aims to determine whether the data for each research variable is normal or not. The data normality test used in this research is the Lilliefors normality test. Normality test for creative dance learning (X1) and traditional dance learning (X2) calculated by IBM SPSS Statistics 20, the results of the normality test are described in the table below.

Test of Normality							
	Class	Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistics	df	Sig.	Statistics	df	Sig.
Observation Results	Creative Dance Learning	,171	20	,128	,926	20	,131
	Learning Traditional Dance	.111	20	,200*	,959	20	,521

Table 1. Normality Test Results for Creative Dance Learning (X1) and Traditional Dance Learning (X2)

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Based on the results of the data processing output above, it can be concluded that the normality of creative dance learning (X1) in the experimental class is known to be Shapiro-Wilk > 0.05 , namely $0.131 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the data in creative dance learning (X1) in the experimental class is normally distributed. Furthermore, the normality of traditional dance learning (X2) in the control class is known to be Shapiro-Wilk > 0.05 , namely $0.521 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the traditional dance learning data (X2) in the control class is normally distributed.

Homogeneity Test

The homogeneity of variance test is described to test the equality of variables. From the analysis process with IBM SPSS Statistics 20, the homogeneity results obtained are presented in the Test of Homogeneity of Variance table.

Test of Homogeneity of Variance

		Levene Statistics	df1	df2	S ig.
Observation Results	Based on Mean	,953	1	38	,335
	Based on Median	,849	1	38	,363
	Based on the Median andwith adjusted df	,849	1	28,602	,365
	Based on trimmed mean	,852	1	38	,362

Table 2. Homogeneity Test Results for Creative Dance Learning (X1) and Traditional Dance Learning (X2)

Based on the data processing above, it is known that the significance value (Sig) Based on Mean is $0.335 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the variance of the experimental class post-test and control class post-test groups is the same or homogeneous. Thus, one of the sample t-test hypothesis tests can be fulfilled.

Hypothesis test

Based on normality and homogeneity testing of the experimental class and control class, the results show that the analysis requirements in this research are normally distributed and have a homogeneous population variance. This shows that the analysis requirements in this research are met so that it can be continued with further testing, namely testing the hypothesis with the "t" test (Sudijono, 2009) with the following calculations.

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
OBSERVATION RESULT S	Equal Variances assumed	,953	,335	6,761	38	,000	10,050	1,487	7,041	13,059
	Equal variance snot assumed			6,761	32,174	,000	10,050	1,487	7,023	13,077

Table 3. Hypothesis Testing

Based on the results of data processing with IBM SPSS Statistics 20, "Independent Sample Test" in the Equal variances assumed section, it is known that the Sig (2-tailed) value is $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be interpreted that the basis for decision making in the independent sample t-test can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. Thus it can be concluded that there is a significant (real) difference between the average results of increasing self-confidence for children aged 5-6 years at RA Kairu Ummah in the creative dance learning group (experimental) and the learning group traditional dance (control).

Decision-making is based on the calculated t value with the t table in the independent sample t-test, the following decision is obtained. It is known that the tcount value is 6,761. Next, consulting the ttable at the 5% and 1% levels with $dk = (N_1 + N_2) - 2 = 38$, we obtained a significance level of 5% = 2.42 and a significance level of 1% = 2.71. After consultation, it turned out that the tcount obtained was greater than ttable, namely $2.00 < 6,761 > 2.65$. This means that H_a is accepted, namely that there is a significant influence between learning dance on the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years at RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal in the 2022/2023 academic year.

DISCUSSION

The research results went through several stages of activity. The research variable consists of two groups, namely the experimental group (X1) using the song "Naik Kereta Api" with creative dance learning and the control group (X2) using traditional dance with the song "Zapim Melayu". The research stages began with testing the validity and reliability of the

instrument which was tested on 20 students. The results of IBM SPSS Statistics 20 calculations, the results of the validity of statement items in the self-confidence observation sheet for children 5-6 years old, all statement items are declared valid, because in each statement item the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$. The results of calculating the reliability of the self-confidence questionnaire for children 5-6 years old obtained r_{11} and after consulting the interval scale for the level of correlation strength, the correlation coefficient of the self-confidence observation sheet statement for children 5-6 years old was in the high category $r_{count} > r_{table}$ or Cronbach's Alpha $0.749 > 0.444$, so the instrument stated to have high reliability.

Valid instruments will be used to collect experimental and control data at the observation stage in each class. Research variable data for creative dance learning classes for experimental classes applied to class B1, for ages 5-6 years with a sample size of 20 children consisting of 13 girls and 7 boys. Indicators from the observation sheet are 1) completing work well, 2) being firm, 3) being firm in your beliefs, 4) daring to lead appropriately and without hesitation, 5) being able to work together with others, 6) doing tasks independently, 7) Think logically, 8) have a good perspective in dealing with everything. The results of data processing used IBM SPSS Statistics 20 calculations. The average creative dance learning class (experimental) was 39.85, the highest total score was 50 and the lowest was 20.

Research variable data for creative dance learning classes for the control class applied to class B3, for ages 5-6 years with a sample size of 20 children consisting of 15 girls and 5 boys. Indicators from the observation sheet are 1) completing work well, 2) being firm, 3) being firm in your beliefs, 4) daring to lead appropriately and without hesitation, 5) being able to work together with others, 6) doing tasks independently, 7) Think logically, 8) have a good perspective in dealing with everything. The average of the traditional dance learning class (control) was 29.80, the highest total score was 35 and the lowest was 22.

The average result of the creative dance learning class (experimental) was 39.85, which was different from the average of the traditional dance learning class (control) which was 29.80. Difference range 10.05. These results confirm the opinion of Wulandari (2019), concluding that the research results show that the application of creative dance is quite good. The benefits of creative dance activities can be seen in changes in children's kinesthetic development.

The data collected after the data description is carried out, the analysis prerequisite tests are carried out, namely the normality and homogeneity tests, and finally the hypothesis test. The results of the normality processing output for creative dance learning (X1) in the experimental class using the song "Riding the Train" are known to be Shapiro-Wilk > 0.05 , namely $0.131 > 0.05$, it can be concluded that the data for creative dance learning (X1) in the experimental class has a normal distribution. Furthermore, the normality of traditional dance learning (X2) in the control class with the song "Zapim Melayu" is known to be Shapiro-Wilk > 0.05 , namely $0.521 > 0.05$, it can be

concluded that the traditional dance learning data (X₂) in the control class is normally distributed. Next, a homogeneity test was carried out. Based on processing, it is known that the significance value (Sig) Based on Mean is $0.335 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the variance of the experimental class post-test group and the control class post-test group is the same or homogeneous.

Testing the normality and homogeneity of the experimental class and control class showed that in this study the analysis requirements were normally distributed and the population variance was homogeneous. The results of data processing with IBM SPSS Statistics 20, "Independent Sample Test" on the same Equal variances assumed, it is known that the Sig (2-tailed) value is $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be interpreted as a basis for decision making in independent sample t-test it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. From this, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the average results of the formation of self-confidence for children aged 5-6 years in the creative dance learning group (experiment) and the traditional dance learning group (control). RA Kairu Ummah.

Making decisions based on the value of t_{count} with t_{table} in the independent sample t test resulted in the following decision. It is known that the t_{count} value is 6,761. Next, consulting the t_{table} at the 5% and 1% levels with $dk = (N_1 + N_2) - 2 = 38$, we obtained a significance level of 5% = 2.42 and a significance level of 1% = 2.71. After consultation, it turned out that the t_{count} obtained was greater than t_{table} , namely $2.00 < 6,761 > 2.65$. This means that H_a is accepted, namely that there is a significant influence between learning dance on the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years at RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal in the 2022/2023 academic year. These results are in line with Silastri (2022), results of research conducted by researchers regarding the influence of creative dance movements on the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years in PAUD Bandar Agung Village, South Bengkulu. It was concluded that the creativity of dance movements influences the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years in PAUD Bandar Agung Village, South Bengkulu. These results are not much different from the results of RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal's research for the 2022/2023 academic year, namely that there is a significant influence between learning dance on the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results and discussion of research on the influence of learning dance on the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years at RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal for the 2022/2023 academic year, it is concluded that there is a significant influence between learning dance on the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years in RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal academic year 2022/2023. Data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 20, "Independent Sample Test" in the Equal variances assumed section shows that the Sig value (2-tailed) is $0.000 < 0.05$, it is concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.

Also, the tcount obtained is greater than ttable. namely $2.00 < 6,761 > 2.65$. Thus it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the average results of increasing self-confidence for children aged 5-6 years at RA Kairu Ummah in the creative dance learning group (experimental) and the learning group traditional dance (control).

Recommendations

There are several suggestions that researchers recommend from the results of research on the Influence of Dance Learning on the Self-Confidence of Children Aged 5-6 Years at RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal for the 2022/2023 Academic Year, including:

1. To the school and teacher RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal, support and motivation from teachers are very important factors in implementing creative dance learning to increase children's self-confidence.
2. RA Khairu Ummah Sunggal's children can make more independent movements so that the teacher can direct the children in a better direction.
3. To future researchers, the results of this research have shortcomings, in terms of the application of dance by connecting it with children's self- confidence. The researcher hopes that future researchers will study more widely the relationship between dance and children's self-confidence

ADVANCED RESEARCH

For advanced research, we hope that advanced research can research and use innovative ways to increase the self-confidence of children aged 5-6 years.

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